

The Influence of Village Apparatus Competence and Village Fund Management on Increasing Community Welfare in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency

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Abstract:- The level of community welfare in Piloliyanga village still needs to be improved. Some people are still at the lower middle income level. Village officials have a role in improving the welfare of village communities. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of village apparatus competence and village financial management on improving community welfare. The population in this research is all the people in Piloliyanga village. Sampling using random sampling technique. The data analysis technique in this research uses multiple linear regression analysis. The results showed that the role of the village apparatus and the management of village funds greatly contributed to and influenced the welfare of the people in Piloliyanga village. With the existence of village apparatus who are skilled and professional and able to manage village funds and contribute to village development with the right target, it will have an impact on increasing the welfare of the people in Piloliyanga village.

Keywords:- Village Apparatus Competence; Village Fund Management; Community Welfare.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Law Number 6 of 2014 states that a village is a village and a customary village or what is referred to by another name, hereinafter referred to as a Village, is a legal community unit that has territorial boundaries that are authorized to regulate and manage government affairs, the interests of the local community based on recognized initiatives. and respected in the system of government of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. With the passing of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, villages are given a great opportunity to manage their own governance and implement development to improve the welfare and quality of life of village communities. The law on villages, along with its implementing regulations, has mandated village governments to be more independent in managing their governance. As the lowest unit of a national government system, the village government is faced with very difficult conditions as a result of the change in government paradigm from centralized to decentralized (Rasman, 2014)

One important element that urgently needs to be prepared in relation to the implementation of village autonomy is the village government apparatus. Based on Government Regulation Number 43 of 2014 concerning village apparatus which states that the village government is the village head or what is referred to by another name assisted by village officials as elements of village government administration who have sufficient ability or competence to encourage the improvement of village apparatus government performance.

The village apparatus as the administrator of the village government is given the authority to manage the village so that it becomes more advanced which is solely for the benefit of the wider community. With the law on villages, the village not only receives the remnants of the budget according to the principle of decentralization, but is given the authority to regulate and use village funds according to the needs of the community (Tarjo, 2019)

Village funds are a number of funds and are indeed budgeted by the government for villages. Village funds are taken from the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN) and have indeed been allocated to villages at least 10% of the APBN and will later be disbursed to villages through three stages, the first stage is distributed by 20%, the second and third stages are 40%. Funds that have been given must be used and managed properly and under control. Every activity whose funds are taken from village funds, must go through several stages such as good planning, structured implementation, and clear evaluation in accordance with governance principles.

However, the reality on the ground is that there are many villages that are less than optimal in terms of the performance of village officials and in the management of village funds which has an impact on the level of welfare of the village community. The ability to plan village development programs and activities, process administration, as well as the level of village apparatus' control is still not optimal. In terms of managing village funds, such as budget allocations and targets for the number of recipients of village funds, they are still not optimal. This happened in Piloliyanga village, which is a village located in Talamuta District, Boalemo Regency, Gorontalo Province, Indonesia.

Seeing from what has been explained above about the problems above, the authors are interested in studying further and in depth through research with the research title: "The Influence of Village Apparatus Competence and Village Fund Management on Increasing Community Welfare in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency".

II. METHOD

This study used quantitative analysis with the research location in the village of Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency. This type of research was chosen to reveal and identify the competence development of the village apparatus and the management of the use of village funds in improving the welfare of the people in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency. The sampling technique in this study was using random sampling which was taken randomly from the people in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency. To support the research results, SPSS Statistics Version 26 software was used to analyze the research data obtained. The tests used in this study are data quality testing, classical assumption testing, and multiple linear regression analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the calculation of descriptive statistics with the help of SPSS 26, the criteria for the variable tendency of Village Apparatus Competence (X1), Village Fund Management (X2), and community welfare (Y) are obtained in the following frequency distribution table.

Table 1. Village Apparatus Competency Frequency Distribution

No	Range	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	> 55	Very High	30	28,84
2	51 - 55	High	42	40,38
3	45 - 50	Low	23	22,11
4	< 45	Very Low	9	8,65
Total			104	100

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the frequency distribution above, it shows that the Competence of Village Apparatuses is in the high category, namely 40.38%, while 28.84% are in the very high category, 22.11% are in the low category, and 8.65% of students have Village Apparatus Competence. very low category.

Table 2. Village Fund Management Frequency Distribution

No	Range	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	> 55	Very High	22	21,15
2	51 - 55	High	47	45,19
3	45 - 50	Low	19	18,26
4	< 45	Very Low	16	15,38
Total			104	100

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the frequency distribution above, it shows that Village Fund Management is high, namely as much as 45.19%, while 21.49% is in the very high category, 22.03% is in the low category, and 15.38% has Village Fund Management which is in the low category.

Table 3. Community Welfare Frequency Distribution

No	Range	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	$X \geq 55$	Very High	35	33,65
2	$51 \leq X < 55$	High	47	45,19
3	$45 \leq X < 50$	Low	23	22,11
4	$X < 45$	Very Low	9	8,75
Total			118	100

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the frequency distribution above, it shows that the welfare of the people in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency, is in the very high category, namely 33.65%, while 45.19% is in the high category, 22.11% is in the low category, and 8.75 % of students have very low social welfare. Before testing the hypothesis, a prerequisite analysis test is carried out, namely the normality test, linearity test, and multicollinearity test. Analysis prerequisite test was carried out with the help of SPSS 22, the results are presented as follows:

Table 4. Normality Test Result

Variable	Significance	Description
Village Apparatus Competency	0.156	Normally distributed
Village Fund Management	0.136	Normally distributed
Community Welfare	0.234	Normally distributed

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the results of the normality test in the table above, it can be stated that the significant value for the Village Apparatus Competence variable is 0.156, Village Fund Management is 0.136 and Community Welfare is 0.234 at a significant level of ≥ 0.05 , because the significance value of the three variables is ≥ 0.05 , so the data can be stated that the data the three variables are normally distributed.

Table 5. Linearity Test Results

Variable	Sig.	Description
Village Apparatus Competence (X1) on Community Welfare (Y)	0,710	Linier
Village Fund Mangement (X ₂) on Community Welfare (Y)	0,757	Linier

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the results of the linearity test in the table above, the linearity test for Village Apparatus Competence (X1) on Community Welfare (Y) obtained a significance value of 0.710 greater than 0.05 so that the two have a linear relationship. The

linearity test between the Village Fund Management variable (X2) and Community Welfare (Y) obtained a significance value of 0.757 greater than 0.05, so this variable has a linear relationship.

Table 6. Multicollinearity Test Results

Independent Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Description
Village Apparatus Competence (X ₁)	0,878	1,245	No Multicollinearity
Village Fund Management (X ₂)	0,877	1,145	No Multicollinearity

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the table above, it is known that the tolerance value for the Village Apparatus Competence variable (X1) and Village Fund Management (X2) is 0.878 which is greater than 0.1 and the VIF value is 1.245 which is less than 10.00 so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity in the two variables the.

After the prerequisite analysis test was carried out and the results were fulfilled, then the hypothesis test was carried out. The first hypothesis of this study is: there is a contribution of Village Apparatus Competence (X1) to Community Welfare (Y). Testing the first hypothesis using simple regression analysis with the help of SPSS version 26.0. The results of hypothesis testing are as follows.

Table 7. First Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	R value	R ² value	T value	Coefficient	Const.	Description
X ₁ -Y	0,370	0,137	4,016	0,321	35,764	Positive and significant

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the table above, the regression equation is $Y = 35.764 + 0.321 X_1$. This equation shows that the regression coefficient value is positive by 0.321, meaning that if the value of the Village Apparatus Competency variable (X1) increases by one unit, community welfare (Y) will increase by 0.321 units. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.137$) is 0.370, meaning that the Village Apparatus Competency variable (X1) contributes 37% to community welfare (Y).

The results of testing hypothesis 1 (H1) show that the competence of village government officials affects the welfare of the Piloliyanga village community, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency. The significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$ so that the proposed hypothesis is accepted. This result is also in line with the research of Amalia & Maryono (2022), Huda (2019), Inapti & Rakhmawati (2022), which shows that the more competent the apparatus managing village finances, the welfare of the community will increase. The competence of a village apparatus can be seen from several indicators, namely the understanding of village apparatus in managing village funds and coordinating a number of village apparatus. In addition, village officials need to have technical expertise in managing village funds. Competent village apparatus must understand the main tasks, functions and job descriptions in preparing village fund financial reports.

Village officials also need to increase training to support their understanding in becoming quality village apparatus. This can improve the ability to prepare financial reports which have implications for improving people's welfare. Another thing that must be owned by the village apartur is the initiative to work and a staffing code of ethics to support the success of the village apparatus in managing village funds and to improve the welfare of the village community. "To improve village welfare, competence is needed. With regard to village funds, of course, the competence of qualified human resources is very much needed. Human resource competence is needed for village financial management and accountability" (Umaira, 2019). "The competence of the village apparatus is seen as the ability to achieve a certain performance. Human resources include

education, work experience, and training (Kristianto, 2018). This means that the more competent the village apparatus is in managing village finances, the more village welfare will be from managing village funds. Conversely, if the village apparatus does not have adequate resources to carry out their duties, village welfare will not be achieved "(Umaira, 2019). The success of managing village funds is greatly influenced by how the leader manages a given fund. In this case the competence of the village government apparatus has a very important role so that village funds are able to be absorbed properly, especially the competence of the village head himself (Agustini, 2017).

The results of this study indicate that village funds have a positive and significant relationship to community welfare. This means that village funds will affect people's welfare. With regard to the disbursement of village funds and the allocation of village funds, it is expected that the regional development process as a whole will be enhanced and together the development disparities between regions will also be reduced. The government has a very important position in creating distributinal justice, because creating prosperity in society is the obligation of all economic agents. Besides that, the government also acts as a guarantor for the creation of fair distribution and becomes a facilitator of human development and creates community welfare (Pitri, 2018). The competence of the village apparatus is needed so that the management of village funds can develop in various aspects. For this reason, in practice, village apparatus must have intelligence, knowledge and skills related to their work. This is a form of responsibility of the village apparatus in carrying out village government activities "(Widiawaty, 2019).

Competence is needed by a village apparatus. With the existence of competence can improve the quality of himself so as to produce maximum performance. A village official who does not have competence will do the work longer and not fit the purpose. The results of this study indicate that the competency of the village apparatus positively influences or

contributes to the welfare of the community in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency.

The second hypothesis of this study is: there is a contribution of Village Fund Management (X2) to community

welfare (Y). Testing the second hypothesis using simple regression analysis with the help of SPSS version 26.0. The results of hypothesis testing are as follows.

Table 8. Second Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	R value	R ² value	T value	Coefficient	Const.	Description
X ₂ -Y	0,597	0,357	7,518	0,689	16,015	Positive and significant

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the table above, the regression equation is $Y = 16.015 + 0.689 X_2$. This equation shows that the regression coefficient value is positive by 0.387, meaning that if the value of the Village Fund Management variable (X₂) increases by one unit, community welfare (Y) will increase by 0.689 units. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = x_1 y^2$) is 0.357, which means that the Village Fund Management variable (X₂) contributes 35.7% to community welfare (Y).

The results of testing hypothesis 2 (H₂) show that the competence of village government officials affects the welfare of the Piloliyanga village community, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency. The significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$ so that the proposed hypothesis is accepted. This result is also in line with the research of Amalia & Maryono (2022), Huda (2019), Inapti & Rakhmawati (2022), which shows that the more competent the apparatus managing village finances, the welfare of the community will increase. The competence of a village apparatus can be seen from several indicators, namely the understanding of village apparatus in managing village funds and coordinating a number of village apparatus. In addition, village officials need to have technical expertise in managing village funds. Competent village apparatus must understand the main tasks, functions and job descriptions in preparing village fund financial reports.

Village officials also need to increase training to support their understanding in becoming quality village apparatus. This can improve the ability to prepare financial reports which have implications for improving people's welfare. Another thing that must be owned by the village apartur is the initiative to work and a staffing code of ethics to support the success of the village apparatus in managing village funds and to improve the welfare of the village community. "To improve village welfare, competence is needed. With regard to village funds, of course, the competence of qualified human resources is very much needed. Human resource competence is needed for village financial management and accountability" (Umaira, 2019). "The competence of the village apparatus is seen as the ability to achieve a certain performance. Human resources include education, work experience, and training (Kristianto, 2018). This means that the more competent the village apparatus is in managing village finances, the more village welfare will be from managing village funds. Conversely, if the village

apparatus does not have adequate resources to carry out their duties, village welfare will not be achieved" (Umaira, 2019). The success of managing village funds is greatly influenced by how the leader manages a given fund. In this case the competence of the village government apparatus has a very important role so that village funds are able to be absorbed properly, especially the competence of the village head himself (Agustini, 2017).

The results of this study indicate that village funds have a positive and significant relationship to community welfare. This means that village funds will affect people's welfare. With regard to the disbursement of village funds and the allocation of village funds, it is expected that the regional development process as a whole will be enhanced and together the development disparities between regions will also be reduced. The government has a very important position in creating distributional justice, because creating prosperity in society is the obligation of all economic agents. Besides that, the government also acts as a guarantor for the creation of fair distribution and becomes a facilitator of human development and creates community welfare (Pitri, 2018).

The competence of the village apparatus is needed so that the management of village funds can develop in various aspects. For this reason, in practice, village apparatus must have intelligence, knowledge and skills related to their work. This is a form of responsibility of the village apparatus in carrying out village government activities" (Widiawaty, 2019). Competence is needed by a village apparatus. With the existence of competence can improve the quality of himself so as to produce maximum performance. A village official who does not have competence will do the work longer and not fit the purpose. The results of this study indicate that Village Fund Management contributes positively to the welfare of the community in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency.

The third hypothesis of this study is: there is a simultaneous contribution of Village Apparatus Competence (X₁) and Village Fund Management (X₂) to Community Welfare (Y). Testing the third hypothesis using multiple regression analysis with the help of SPSS version 26.0. The results of hypothesis testing are as follows.

Table 9. Third Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	R value	R ² value	F value	Coefficient	Const.	Description
X ₁	0,598	0,358	28,165	0,659	15,367	Positive and significant
X ₂				0,41		

Source: Results of Primary Data Processing

Based on the table above, the regression equation is $Y = 15.367 + 0.659X_1 - 0.41X_2$. This equation shows that the regression coefficient value is positive by 0.659, meaning that if the Village Apparatus Competency value (X_1) increases by one unit, community Welfare (Y) will increase by 0.659 units assuming Village Fund Management (X_2) remains the same. The coefficient value of Village Fund Management (X_2) is negative 0.41, meaning that if the value of Village Fund Management (X_2) increases by one unit, community welfare (Y) will increase by 0.41 units assuming the Competence of Village Apparatus (X_1) remains constant. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.358, which means that Village Apparatus Competence (X_1) and Village Fund Management (X_2) simultaneously contribute 35.8% to community welfare (Y) and the remaining 64.2% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

IV. CONCLUSION

Efforts to improve the welfare of the village community in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency can be pursued with good support and participation from village officials and the ability to manage village funds wisely and well. Based on the results of the study it can be concluded that: (1) Competence of Village Apparatus contributes positively to the welfare of the people of Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency (2) Management of Village Funds contributes positively to welfare and (3) Competence of Village Apparatus and Management of Village Funds simultaneously contributes positively to community welfare in Piloliyanga Village, Tilamuta District, Boalemo Regency. Quality human resources can be seen from their educational background, training they have attended, skills stated in carrying out their duties and job descriptions, so that the competence of the village apparatus encourages accountability for managing village funds of a higher quality, free from corruption, collusion and nepotism practices. Which can improve the welfare of society. Village apparatus can use it instead of controlling absolutely village funds and village fund allocations but must be used wisely and responsibly in efforts to improve welfare in order to reduce poverty so that they become better economically and have a better quality of life.

From these results, it is recommended for the Piloliyanga village apparatus, in order to be able to maintain and improve their performance and increase their self-competence so that the management of village funds can run well. For village communities, it is expected that they will always supervise the performance of the village government and participate in providing input and suggestions for the village government in managing village funds for community development and welfare. For the government or related agencies in the future,

village readiness is needed through strengthening human resource capacity, besides that the government also needs to provide more focused and sustainable guidance, assistance and monitoring to villages. On the other hand, it is necessary to strengthen coordination, consolidation and synergy in the implementation of programs/activities that become village development priorities from the Central Government, Regency, District Government to the village level.

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